

Learning Conceptual Modeling Design Through the Classutopia Serious Game

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One of the more complex topics to teach to Software Engineering students is the conceptual modeling design, which has several concepts that students must learn in order to specify the structural, behavioral and interaction views of software systems. Learning the design of class diagrams is of paramount importance since these diagrams are used to guide concrete development tasks such as programming and testing, and, consequently, to avoid defective software products. Applying novel teaching/learning techniques in this topic may help students to reduce the defects that are committed at the moment of designing a class diagram. One interesting technique is the use of serious games, since they provide learning environments free of risks and pressure for students, allowing the students to know the topics that they must learn in a funny way. Serious games have been widely used in programming courses. We aim to investigate the feasibility to replicate this experience for conceptual modeling of class diagrams at Software Engineering courses. In this paper, we present a role-playing game especially focused on the class diagram, which is called Classutopia. This serious game provides modeling challenges, comprehension and correction of diagrams with different complexity levels for learning conceptual modeling design.

Keywords: Gamification; serious games; class diagram; software engineering course.

1. Introduction

Conceptual modeling is one of the more complex topics that must be learnt by Software Engineering students since they need to abstract concepts from reality and express them in computational terms. The conceptual modeling design is of paramount importance in the development of software projects because it specifies the different views of a software system, which guide the programming and the testing tasks. The class diagram is one of the most representative design approaches for software modeling [1], which serves as a guideline to develop the structures and the methods of a software product. A faulty class diagram misleads the software development teams, leading to mistakes in coding and delays in project implementations, and subsequently causing project failures.

Some common defects encountered in the development of class diagrams [2–5] are as follows: confusion amidst elements such as aggregation and composition, overspecification, errors in the cardinality, i.e. creating infinite recursive associations, poor

choices of names for classes and attributes, class replications, lack of inheritance between classes of the same type, lack of classes and attributes, and lost methods.

The defects mentioned above can be overcome if the students actively participate in the learning process. The use of games and simulation-based experiences has been of great help for teaching, where games are offering learning environments without any risk for the students. These games may be played seriously or casually [6]. The games that have been explicitly designed for an educational purpose and not to solely entertain have been defined as serious games [6, 7]. Moreover, the use of video game characteristics such as points or rewards in a game is known as gamification. Currently, there are several systematic reviews in the literature [8, 9] that have reported the positive results of serious game-based learning, wherein the use of this type of game has been verified in various domains of learning in topics related to health, education (school and university), culture, social skills and vocational training, among others. Within the domain of education, specifically in the computing area [10], it has been widely used to teach topics such as programming, project management software and operating systems. It is also significant that most of the primary studies were conducted within the past five years, indicating that this teaching/learning methodology is relatively new and apparently trendy [9].

We believe that by implementing serious games, specifically focused on learning conceptual modeling, it is possible to motivate and entertain students by modifying their behavior in a positive manner when coping with class diagrams. Therefore, the design of a serious game for learning and understanding conceptual modeling design is presented in this paper. The game is a role-playing game (RPG) wherein a character hero (characterized by a robot) is assigned to a player who must complete an adventure by overcoming three types of challenges to defeat the villains (characterized as evil wizards). This game is called Classutopia. As the game progresses, the difficulty of the challenges will increase based on the predefined problems. The three challenges are the following:

- . Modeling a class diagram, which allows to build and improve the character class diagram as the adventure advances.
- . Understanding a class diagram, which will allow the character to heal from damages caused by the enemy by answering questions based on the observation of a diagram.
- . Recognizing class diagram flaws, which will allow the character to determine the defects in class diagrams injected by the enemies, and correct the defects identified in order to revert in damaging the opposition.

Considering that the target users for the game devised in this work would be students from the Software Engineering course, most of whom are youngsters who have grown up under exposure to the latest technologies and that a large part of them have one, or more, of the aforementioned mobile devices, it has been decided to build the game as a mobile application for the most popular operating systems Android and iOS. Therefore, students will have easy access to the application and can use it daily without obstacles. With this in mind, the implementation of Classutopia was conducted using the game engine Unity [22] since it allows simultaneous construction of multi-platform games.

Therefore, the contribution of this work is the design of a serious game for conceptual modeling learning of the class diagram and the implementation of a mobile application for

Android that provides support for running the game on tablets. This contribution is useful for students who want to learn how to do a class model design avoiding defects, for professors who can use the serious game as a fresh technique to practice conceptual modeling of class diagrams and also for researchers who want to add new challenges to the Classutopia serious game.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents some relevant related works. Section 3 presents the design of a serious game developed for learning conceptual modeling of the class diagram. Section 4 presents the evaluation of the game. Finally, Sec. 5 presents the main conclusions and future works.

2. Related Works

The use of serious games in education has been widely studied in the last decade, since they are conceived as fresh techniques to improve the teaching/learning experience. Proof of that includes the following systematic literature reviews [17–20] that exhibit works that apply serious games or gamification to educational contexts.

In [19], the relationship between gamification and the educational context was investigated. Results of this review present 119 studies, out of which 9% were applied to K12, 43% were applied to university level and 48% were applied to training in industry. In addition, in the systematic review presented in [17], which presents 34 studies, 5% were focused on primary and secondary education whereas 95% were focused on higher education and training. This supports the statement that gamification and serious games have been widely applied to education at different educational levels, but university level is the one where research has been done most widely due to the complexity of contents.

In [18], the systematic review with 27 selected studies was focused on investigating the goal of using gamification or serious games in different education levels. The results show that the goal of using gamification by these studies corresponds to producing a behavioral change by motivating the students, and therefore as a second step improve learning. Moreover, in [17] authors present the game elements that have been used in gamifying educational systems, where badges are used massively as rewards to improve learning by producing behavioral change and engagement.

In [20], the state of game-based learning in engineering education is presented. This literature review is comprised of 191 papers, which provide evidence about students enjoying game-based learning.

The systematic reviews of literature on serious games and gamification presented above reveal that the main focus of the studies is the engagement and motivation of students by means of challenges, levels, medals and rewards. This prompted us to create a serious game to improve the motivation and engagement of the conceptual modeling learning of Software Engineering students.

Even though there are several serious games published in literature, as we can observe in the systematic literature reviews presented in [8, 9], we did not find literature of serious games that had been applied to specifically teaching/learning conceptual modeling by using a class diagram. Nevertheless, some of the games that are focused on teaching object-oriented programming concepts are closely linked to the modeling of classes, so we review these documents in this section.

Java Ninja [11] evaluated the effects of utilizing serious games focused on teaching specific concepts of modeling and programming, wherein the students receive help in understanding exclusively the inheritance concept in object-oriented programming and show positive results in their learning processes and motivation. To do that, students must code a subclass from a superclass using Java language and the game shows the UML class diagram and the ninja.

In [12] a game-theme instructional model is presented, which demonstrates the concepts of object-oriented programming, specifically encapsulation, polymorphism and inheritance. The game uses virtual reality to engage students with three problems related to the programming topics mentioned above. The student must answer correctly in the inheritance situation in order to construct a class model diagram. Results indicate that 80% of students agreed that the module developed their interest in programming.

In [13] a game focused on object-oriented programming concepts is presented. In this game, the players can select an object and the class diagram is displayed in order to show the inheritance relationships of the selected object.

A serious game focused on the education of object-oriented analysis and design and artificial intelligence is presented in [14]. The game is about the Sokoban problem, where five types of relationships can be identified: association, composition, dependency, inheritance and aggregation. Authors state that to facilitate applying serious game a promising strategy would be accumulating and opening game-based materials. So, they provide this game with a puzzle style, but no information is provided about the usage or empirical evaluations.

In summary, we did not find serious games specifically focused on learning conceptual modeling design, nevertheless clear examples of the use of class diagrams in challenges of serious games have been obtained. For instance, the Java Ninja game allows students to understand the inheritance concept. Considering the importance and difficulty of conceptual modeling learning in Software Engineering, and that it is important to know different conceptual constructs not only inheritance, a serious game has been created specifically for class diagram learning, which is shown in the next section.

3. Design of Classutopia Serious Game

The design of a serious game for the conceptual modeling of class diagram learning has been developed using the engine Unity [22], aiming toward its execution in a mobile application for devices with Android operating system. The conceptual framework of Mechanics–Dynamics–Aesthetics (MDA) [15] is used to explain the design of the game, which allows the implementation of the game by taking into account the player and the developer viewpoints.

3.1. Aesthetics

For making the game attractive and funny for the player, the game has a minimalist graphic style, displaying easy-to-interpret buttons, lists and menus. In a similar way, common visual representations of RPG games are used, such as health bars, characters' dialog

windows and sprites for the same. The visual feedback of the player's interaction with the elements on the screen is based on the changes of hues and approaches.

Moreover, an interesting context has been created to motivate playing the game. Classutopia is a technological utopia wherein human beings have reached the pinnacle of civilization thanks to the help of technology. Amidst all significant technological advances achieved, five are considered the most important, called The Pillars, in which all this social prosperity is underpinned: a satellite plant of solar energy, a synthesized food system, an organ cultivation center, an anti-pollution multi-industrial system and a robots factory for unwanted tasks.

All the basic needs of humanity (health, food and energy) have been met. The villain in this story is the last descendant of a caste of sorcerers, who is bothered by the fact that humanity has reached fullness thanks to technology and not magic. Therefore, he has initiated an attempt to sabotage The Pillars, making use of his magic tricks to modify this systems software by altering the class models to overthrow the utopia. However, a maintenance robot has become aware of these failures; the reason why it pursues an original adventure to repair the damages and ruin the sorcerer's plans. This context works as a guideline for the creation of the diagrams arranged for the missions since each mission represents the robot's attempt to save one of The Pillars. A diagram is modeled to represent the satellite plant of solar energy, synthesized food system and organ cultivation center; these diagrams are presented in the missions 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Classutopia is available for download at:
<https://www.dropbox.com/s/sfcjjz0jlp6a911/Classutopia.apk?dl%0>.

3.2. Mechanics

The game is based on three types of mechanics: modeling the character, correcting defective diagrams and understanding diagrams.

3.2.1. Character modeling

The main character is a robot with three basic attributes: attack, defense and speed. Attack relates to the damage the protagonist can cause to the enemy, defense is the resistance posed to the damage received from the enemy and speed is the management of the limited time to solve the problems. These attributes can be modified and enhanced through modeling of class diagrams, which describe the features and components of the robot. Initially, the robot needs to be modeled correctly, and subsequently, as the game progresses, new improvements can be unlocked, which should be properly included in the class model of the robot so that the changes take effect. These improvements, in addition to modifying the character's attributes, also unlock some special powers that can be used in the clashes between the protagonist robot and its enemy (the magician).

3.2.2. Correction of defective diagrams

During the game, the hero battles against the enemy; the disputes are based on the challenge of correcting defective class diagrams. In these challenges, given a defective class diagram,

the player can tap the screen of the tablet to highlight the various elements that make up the class diagram, which has been considered to be defective. Therefore, Classutopia offers options to correct the possible defects. Once the correction has been made, feedback on whether the player has made a mistake or done it correctly is not instantaneous but the player must "Attack" to be able to assess the correction. This has been designed in this manner to give an option to the player to evaluate one or more modifications made to the diagram by pressing a single button, in which mistakes result in harming the protagonist (robot) and the successful corrections affect the enemy (magician). This is graphically presented on the characters' health bars that indicate the status for each character. In addition, Classutopia delivers feedback in the class diagram; it indicates in green the modification that was applied correctly and in red where it has been incorrectly modified. It also includes a button to undo the recently applied modifications.

3.2.3. Understanding diagrams

During the battles, the player can activate special powers in the robot that allow him to perform various effects such as enabling damage modifiers to apply more force on the attacks, reducing corrections in the diagram to finish it on time or healing the protagonist. These modifiers have limited use and are activated by means of a challenge in understanding class diagrams. By pressing the button which activates a certain power, the player must answer a question with respect to the concepts that can be used in a class diagram. This question displays a small diagram or some conceptual construct and offers between two and four possible answers. If the player answers correctly, the power is effective; if answered incorrectly, the effect will not be applied. The powers are arranged in the battle according to the previously modeled characteristics for the robot.

3.3. Dynamics

The mechanics previously described have been presented to the player in a smooth, consistent and understandable way during the execution of the game. To obtain the expected gameplay, a series of screens, menus and systems are implemented, which correspond to the way in which the player interacts with the mechanics of the serious game, i.e. the dynamics. Like most mobile applications available today, the game is controlled via touch screen by simply tapping on buttons and menu items displayed on the screen. In some game mechanics, multi-touch gestures are used to zoom in and out and scroll through the proposed class diagrams.

The development in Unity mixes the use of both the code as well as the graphical user interface to implement the dynamics. To understand this, the different types of elements used for the implementation of Classutopia are explained through the dynamics of Classutopia. We implement scripts in C# (1) to control the questions of conceptual constructs that are shown when the player wants to activate a special power this is related to the understanding diagrams mechanic; (2) to control the battles, which is the central part of the serious game where a class diagram is presented with defects that are automatically generated this is related to the correction of defective diagrams mechanic; (3) to control the objects that represent the improvements of the robot this is related to the character

modeling mechanic; and (4) to control the attributes of the player, i.e. the values of attack, defense, speed and the character's maximum health this is related to the character modeling mechanic and to the correction of defective diagrams mechanic.

3.3.1. Start screen and save game handling

When the player runs the application, a screen is shown with the name of the game, a representative image and a "Start" button to initiate the game. It is a simple landing screen like those of most mobile games. Once the player has clicked on the "Start" button, the button disappears presenting to the player two new options within the

Fig. 1. Game selection. Upper text: Classutopia. Lower left text: START NEW GAME. Lower right text: LOAD PREVIOUS GAME.

same screen (see Fig. 1): one to start a new game and the other to load a previous game. The game uses a system of unitary games, i.e. you can only save one game at a time, therefore, creating a new game automatically deletes the previous game (if any). For this reason, as a precaution, a warning window to confirm deletion is displayed to avoid accidental loss of the game.

The games are saved automatically, indicating this with a symbol at the end of each challenge. If the player presses the button to start a new game, the stored data are reestablished and the game moves on to the main menu. If the player presses the button "Load Previous Game", it goes directly to the main menu preserving the conditions recorded during the last auto-save.

3.3.2. Main menu

The main menu displays three buttons (see Fig. 2): one to access the construction challenge of modeling the main character, one to access the missions menu and one to return to the home screen. In addition, it displays a summary table with the current attributes of the character robot.

The first time the player accesses this screen (when he/she starts a new game), the "Missions" button is disabled in order to force the player to model the character on the construction screen before accessing the missions menu. This is to provoke the player to

exercise the construction of a class diagram, i.e. the first mechanic of the serious game. As we previously define, a game is considered a serious game when it has been constructed specifically for educational purposes.

3.3.3. Build and upgrades

On the construction screen (see Fig. 3), the mechanics of modeling of the character is presented, as has been previously described. Initially, the player must connect the

Fig. 2. Main menu. Upper right text: CURRENT ATTRIBUTES: ATTACK 1, DEFENSE 1, SPEED 1 and HEALTH 100. Left text: BUILD UP and MISSIONS.

Fig. 3. (Color online) Building screen (left: class diagram, right upper: attributes and special powers, right lower: unlocked improvements in red and locked improvements in gray).

classes that represent the parts of the robot correctly, for example, the robot has a core, sensors, extremities and weapons. The player can see, as he/she models the robot appropriately, how its attributes (attack, defense, speed and unique skills) modify according to the characteristics of the diagram.

Defects in modeling during the construction of the diagram result in the nonmodification of the attributes, i.e. the classes do not apply their effects and the features of the robot are not improved. To do that, the class model created by the player is compared with the correct and complete version of the class diagram for the robot. There is a button to save the changes made, continuing to the main menu, which allows the player to use other dynamics.

Within this screen, the list of improvements for the robot is presented. The improvements correspond to new components (e.g. weapons) that have been unlocked, as a reward, each time a mission is completed. If the improved components are adequately included in the model, then the robot increases its attributes and can activate new powers.

3.3.4. Missions

After modeling the robot for the first time, in the main menu, the button to access the missions menu is enabled. The missions correspond to each of the clashes the robot must complete by defeating the magician (see Fig. 4). These tasks are presented as a list and are sequential, i.e. the second mission is enabled when the previous mission is completed, and the third is activated upon completion of the second mission. Each mission is shown with a name and its level of difficulty. The difficulty of the missions is incremental. In the first instance, the game has three missions: the basic level, mid-level and advanced level.

Fig. 4. Missions menu.

The missions can be repeated for practicing or unlocking new rewards (those corresponding to the accomplished level). To start a mission, the player must tap on it, by doing so it gives way to the battle.

Each mission allows the access to the different class diagrams related to the five pillars in Classutopia, i.e. the player can access the battle. In the battle, for each correct answer, the robot knocks the magician, and for each incorrect answer of the player, the magician knocks the robot. Depending on the level of the mission, the class diagram has been

randomly injected with defects, which must be correctly identified by the player to win the mission, as we explain in detail in Sec. 3.3.5. When the player attacks, it is highlighted in green the correct identifications of defects, and in red the wrong ones. This feedback helps students to understand their mistakes.

3.3.5. Battle

The battle screen shows the class diagram to be corrected (as explained in Sec. 3.2), which can be navigated using tactile gestures (see Fig. 5). The class diagram shown in each battle is generated starting from a predefined correct diagram related to a pillar in Classutopia. The avatars that represent the parts in conflict are shown at the top of the screen with their respective health bars and with the remaining time for the mission. The confrontation ends when the time runs out, when one of the parties loses all its health or when all defects are corrected. If the player (robot) wins, the level is completed, regards are awarded, progress of the game is saved and the missions menu appears. If the player (robot) loses, the missions menu appears without rewards but with the option to reattempt to complete the mission.

Fig. 5. Battle screen.

Each level focuses on the correction of different groups of defects that have been injected in the class diagrams. To do that, it is necessary to tap the defective class and identify the defect in the correction panel. Figure 6 shows a correction panel with the following defects: Class without id, Class without name, Classes with attributes without data type and Class with repeated attributes.

Fig. 6. Correction panel.

The defects injected are classified into three levels: basic, medium and advanced. The basic level focuses on learning the essential elements within a class (names and attributes). The medium level focuses on learning the correct specification of services in a class. The advanced level focuses on learning the associations and cardinalities. Table 1 shows the injected defects in each of the levels.

Table 1. Defects injected in Classutopia levels.

Level	Defects
Basic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classes without name Classes without id Classes with repeated attributes Classes with attributes without data type
Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classes without creation service Classes with service without return Classes without visualization of attributes
Advanced	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Associations of wrong type Association without cardinality Minimum cardinality of 1 at both ends Descending cardinality at one end of the association

The more advanced levels include the types of defects of the levels of lesser complexity. These defects are applied randomly at the beginning of a confrontation on a diagram without defects, i.e. the game can generate any of these defects in any of the elements of the class diagram presented in a battle and generate another type of defect, completely different, in the same elements when repeating the mission.

In order to implement the random application of defects to the class diagrams, we assign to each defect type an integer incremental number which represents their difficulty. This number is an index for the defect types. We use different indexes for defects of classes and for defects of associations. In addition, we have assigned to each level a maximum index

which is equivalent to the maximum defect type that could be injected in the level plus one, this last condition allows to create the possibility of not injecting more defects in the level. For example, in the medium level, the maximum index is 8, which corresponds to the seven types of defects that could be injected (see all the defects of basic and medium levels in Table 1) plus one. With this, for each class in the class diagram of every mission, we generate a random number from 1 to the maximum possible in the level of the mission. We apply the same for associations. When the generated number is different from the maximum, we inject this type of defect in the class or association unfolded in the class diagram of a mission. At this point, it is important to remark that the class diagrams of the pillars of Classutopia are not static images but they are deployed dynamically starting from the correct design of each element (class or association) and the defects are injected into them in order to make up the defective diagram.

In summary, there are three corrected class diagrams, each one related to each mission of Classutopia. When the player starts a mission, some defects are randomly injected to the corrected class diagram, and then the diagram dynamically unfolds to the player. Consider that in level 1 the starting class diagram has six classes, each one with an 80% of possibility to have a defect, because the defect index is 5 which includes the possibility to not inject a defect. Let us say three defects are randomly injected in a class, there are 35 different combinations to inject defects in one class. These combinations must be applied to each class of the class diagram resulting in hundreds of different combinations to dynamically deploy the class diagram. The starting class diagram of level 2 has nine classes and the starting class diagram of level 3 has 11 classes and 14 associations, resulting in a huge amount of combinations. We construct the defect injection in this way in order to show different class diagrams to the subjects to engage them and to avoid considering to pass a mission as a boring task.

3.3.6. Special powers

On the battle screen, there are buttons to activate the special skills obtained in the construction of the robot (see Fig. 7). By tapping on a skill, the understanding problem is presented, which must be answered correctly for its activation. An example of this kind of problem is presented in Fig. 8, which asks which type of association is presented in an excerpt of a class diagram with two classes: book and chapter. The possible answers are composition, inheritance, aggregation or contention (the last one does not even correspond to an association).

While this occurs time is not paused. Once the problem is addressed, the battle continues and if answered correctly, the effects of the skill are applied; otherwise the

Fig. 7. Special powers.

Fig. 8. Class diagram understanding question.

effects do not apply. Whether it is answered correctly or incorrectly, the selected skill is disabled for the rest of the combat. The types of effects that the skills have are as follows: multipliers of special powers, health recovery of the protagonist, mission's time manipulation or reduction of remaining defects.

4. Evaluation of Classutopia

An exploratory empirical evaluation of Classutopia has been conducted with the aim of assessing the understanding of the game and the perceived utility to support the conceptual modeling learning in the Software Engineering course. For the design of this activity, the guidelines previously defined in [16] were used. The following research question was defined:

RQ1. Do the students find the use of Classutopia for learning the conceptual design of class diagrams beneficial?

The context of the experiment is included in the Software Engineering course, which is a fourth-year course of the Engineer degree in Computer Science and Telecommunications at the Diego Portales University (Chile). The subjects are students of this course who have already attended classes on conceptual modeling. These classes have been conducted using traditional techniques of teaching/learning such as PowerPoint slides and inspection exercises in diagrams printed on a sheet.

In the experiment, the subjects receive a small description of what is Classutopia and then they must play. They begin building the robot and go through the missions. Finally, the subjects must respond to a questionnaire in order to obtain the perceptions of the usefulness of the game as a new technique of teaching/learning of conceptual modeling in Software Engineering. The sentences of the questionnaire are presented in Table 2, and subjects must answer using a Likert scale, where the scale varies from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree). Moreover, at the end of the survey we put a blank space in order to receive some suggestions that the students want to add.

Table 2. Questionnaire to assess Classutopia.

Sentence
1. Classutopia facilitates the understanding of a class diagram.
2. Classutopia helps determine how to correct a class diagram.
3. Classutopia helps to understand the concepts of the class diagram.
4. I find Classutopia easy to understand.
5. Classutopia allows you to learn about the design of a class diagram in an easier way than by using text.
6. In general, I found Classutopia to be useful.

The operation of the experiment was planned to have a duration of 30min, wherein a brief description of Classutopia is initially given and then the subject starts playing. The first author prepared the material of the experiment, which was piloted by the third author. The subjects received the tablet with the game already installed.

4.1. Operation of the empirical evaluation

The research was conducted in the first semester of 2017 with students who have completed the course of Software Engineering in the second half of 2016. Thirteen students participated voluntarily. Participation in the experiment was not related to the score of the students but the students were urged to make their best effort. The start and end of each student for each mission and the times they had to conduct a mission to win it were registered. It is important to mention that each student should complete mission 1 (M1) to unlock mission 2 (M2) and further complete M2 to unlock mission 3 (M3).

Students were provided with the following description of Classutopia: Imagine a world wherein humanity raised to their maximum apogee thanks to technology. There exist five pillars that correspond to the main technological advances in the world: a solar plant to synthesize food plant, an organ plant, an anti-pollution central system and a robot factory,

which oversees undesirable works. All necessities of humanity have been met by technology; however, a magician who believes in magic instead of technology wants to break these pillars. You are the hero of this story and you must design conceptual models to repair the pillars to confront the magician.

The students had 30min to conduct the activity. However, most subjects wanted to continue playing to defeat the magician. The students realized that each time they earned a mission, they unlocked new features that could improve the robot and they were going to build the robot to improve its attributes. In addition, the subjects used the easier mission to unlock the features thanks that they win many times to build the robot to defeat the most powerful wizard in the last mission. Finally, the students fill the questionnaire.

Despite our efforts to ensure the validity of the empirical evaluation, there are some drawbacks [16] that are detailed below:

Internal validity

Maturation is an important aspect of internal validity since the subjects react differently as time passes. To avoid this, the game was built in such a way to increase the level of difficulty each time a mission is completed, and in addition to the defects presented in each mission, the time to complete a mission changes. This kept the subjects engaged with the game, so we believe that this threat has been contained.

The threat of exchange of information was mitigated because the subjects were explicitly asked not to tell the other players how to interact with the game. However, if students arrived late for the activity and waited for their tablet, they could observe how their classmates interacted with the game and therefore this could be considered as a threat. Nevertheless, in order to contain this threat, we segregate the late students from the other students who were already playing the game.

External validity

The use of students as subjects is usually seen as a threat to the generalization of the evaluation; however, given that the purpose of the experiment is to assess whether Classutopia can be used as a learning technique for the students in the conceptual modeling, obtaining their help to assess whether serious game is a technique that provides benefits for learning is essential.

The number of subjects is limited, since there is a constraint of the number of students in the Software Engineering course. We are aware that with a limited number of subjects, it is not possible to apply statistical techniques to increase confidence in the results. Therefore, we are planning to replicate the experiment in the immediate future.

The creation of the class models used on the missions of Classutopia and defects injected in each of them may have been threatened by the interpretations of the standard and the defect types were made by the first and second authors of this work. To mitigate this threat, the third author of this work reviewed the diagrams and the listing of injected defects obtained from recognized authors in the conceptual modeling, as well as accepted papers in conferences that have a solid program committee.

To reduce the threat of evaluation apprehension, subjects were informed that this activity would have no implication on their grades.

Conclusion validity

Given that the sample of subjects was selected from students who have attended Software Engineering in the second half of 2016, the sample is not heterogeneous, so it can affect the validity of our findings. Nevertheless, this threat is reduced when using students with the same or a similar background [16], as in our empirical evaluation.

4.2. Results

Results are shown in Table 3. This table shows the subject, the time spent in each mission, the number of times that the subject attempted each mission and whether the subject finally won the game or not. It is important to mention that each student should complete M1 to unlock M2, and further complete M2 to unlock M3.

Table 3. Experiment results.

Subject	Time M1	No. M1	Time M2	No. M2	Time M3	No. M3	Win
S1	5	2	13	3	14	7	yes
S2	2	1	25	8			no
S3	3	1	27	6	22	9	yes
S4	4	3	7	2	15	5	yes
S5	5	3	22	5			no
S6	1	1	12	5	7	3	no
S7	3	2	10	4	6	3	yes
S8	11	11	7	2	46	16	no
S9	11	5	37	12	20	8	no
S10	2	1	1	1	6	3	yes
S11	4	2	28	7	21	6	no
S12	4	2	17	5	22	8	yes
S13	3	2	8	2	30	10	yes

It can be observed that seven subjects were able to correctly build the robot and detect all defects injected in the diagrams. Of these seven, three subjects win the game within 30 min but four subjects were engaged for more time in the game to overcome it. Four subjects correctly built the robot but did not exceed M3 that had defects in the associations of the classes. Two subjects did not exceed M2 that had defects in the services of the classes and did not continue to play after 30 min. It is important to note that the four subjects who did not win had to stop playing the game although they were eager to continue playing.

The results indicate that all students (13 subjects) could learn how to build the robot and detect defects in the class attributes (basic level). About 11 of them were able to learn how to build the robot and detect defects at the basic and medium levels, which correspond to defects injected in attributes and services. From these 11 students, seven students could learn how to build the robot and detect defects in the class diagrams at basic, medium and advanced levels, which correspond to defects injected in attributes, services and associations. This allows to observe whether it is feasible to use a serious game for learning the conceptual modeling software, specifically for the construction of a class diagram and to avoid defects in the class diagram. Therefore, the game improves the students' understanding of class diagram, and encourages us to improve the evaluation of the effectiveness in learning.

Regarding the survey, questions 1–3 are related to the perception of the subject matter of learning using the serious game. The results (see Fig. 9) indicate that the students perceive that Classutopia helps in the comprehension of the class diagram and in understanding how to construct a class diagram, and that Classutopia helps to understand the concepts used in the class diagram (the majority of the subjects agree or totally agree with the statements of Q1, Q2 and Q3). Regarding the ease of use of the game (Q4), there are two subjects that did not find it easy to understand how Classutopia works. One of them argued that Classutopia does not have a tutorial that allows to understand how to play, and the other one argued that it is not easy to understand how the special powers work. However, more than 50% of the students

Fig. 9. Results of the questionnaire.

agree or totally agree that it is easy to understand how the game works. Regarding the utility of the game, the majority of students agree that Classutopia allows to learn more easily than using texts (Q5), and they totally agree that in general they found Classutopia to be useful (Q6). The results of this survey allow to answer the research question since the students find it beneficial to use a serious game for learning conceptual modeling, in particular, for learning class diagrams.

In the comments submitted by the subjects, eight subjects agree that it is necessary to add instructions for using the game although as seen in the results, they could play without further explanation. Another improvement mentioned by a subject corresponds to adding details about each power, for example, power fury increases the force of the blows. Although the design elected representative words for each power, we believe it is important to add these improvements in a future version of Classutopia. Six subjects commented that they liked the game, and that they found great the change of the avatar of the enemy for each mission.

From this exploratory empirical evaluation, we have evidence that is feasible to use a serious game to support the learning of conceptual modeling design. Nevertheless, we need more experimentation to add strength and depth to this statement in terms of effectiveness and efficiency.

5. Conclusions

Novel teaching techniques in computer courses are required, particularly for the advanced levels of Software Engineering, because in many cases, the emphasis of research has been placed on the most basic courses such as programming. The design, implementation and use of a serious game to learn conceptual modeling in Software Engineering courses are presented in this work. It is important to note that Classutopia is a serious game since it has been explicitly designed for educational purpose than to solely entertain. From this work, it can be concluded that it is feasible to implement new teaching techniques with gamification and serious games for Software Engineering courses.

In the development of computer projects, modeling a correct class diagram is of vital importance for the reduction of problems and delays in deploying a software. In this work, we provide a solution for the problems caused by the misunderstanding of class diagrams and their semantic components. Thus, Classutopia has been presented, which is a serious game that supports conceptual modeling learning, and it can be a good solution to correct the most common problems that students have to familiarize themselves with while dealing with class diagrams, offering them a space free of pressure and consequences to learn and understand how to model and correct class diagrams. In detail, the defects injected and the understanding questions are related to the following common problems: confusion amidst aggregation and composition, errors in the cardinality, lack of inheritance of classes of the same type, poor choices or lack of names in classes and attributes, visualization of attributes, lack of id and creation service of a class and lack of return of a service of a class.

The choice of a theoretical framework for designing the game provides the team with a simple way to guide the design process covering and ordering correctly all the aspects necessary in a serious game, i.e. the mechanics, dynamics and aesthetics, since the development of serious games considers areas that can move away from the conventional software development. These concepts have been successfully extrapolated for its implementation, making use of the tools and resources offered by the video game engine. Unity, creating a complete and functional application that meets all the items posed in the design. In this way, it has been possible to demonstrate the applicability of serious games for teaching/learning the design of conceptual models by using class diagrams for students in the Software Engineering course.

In addition, there has been an exploratory empirical evaluation to verify the perception of students with respect to this new method of teaching/learning in Software Engineering. Results indicate that Classutopia provides benefits for learning conceptual modeling design. We are aware that with a limited number of subjects, it is not possible to apply statistical techniques to increase confidence in the results. For this reason, we plan to conduct more empirical evaluations as an immediate future work in order to add strength to our results.

One of the limitations of the empirical assessment performed is the lack of evidence of the effectiveness of Classutopia in the learning process. Therefore, further work is aimed to conduct experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of Classutopia by using the F-measure [21], which is based on precision and recall in identifying defects in class diagrams with students playing the serious game and students not playing it.

Finally, there are plans to improve the Classutopia graphics aspects that will help to enhance the gaming experience, and to add a tutorial that will help using the game. Moreover, since this serious game is part of a long-term research about serious games' role in helping to teach/learn Software Engineering, as further work we are planning to add other kinds of models (such as use cases or state transition diagrams) in the Classutopia serious game.

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